

Nitrogen, a gasocrine signal, is likely sensed via ammonia-sensing gasoreceptors

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Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and marks an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine, light-based photocrine, sound-based sonocrine, mineral/metal-based metallochrine, water-based aquacrine, and thermal radiation-based thermocrine signaling. Due to the importance of gasocrine signaling for biotic life, how organisms can sense gasocrine signals such as O_2 (oxygen) via O_2 -sensing protein gasoreceptors (or sensors) has been largely investigated in microorganisms. Even though nitrogen (N_2) is also one of the gasocrine signals, to the best of my knowledge and few other leading experts on nitrogen fixation and nitric oxide-dependent signaling, how organisms sense nitrogen *per se* is still unknown. In my opinion, just as the FeMo (iron-molybdenum) cofactor in nitrogenase can directly bind N_2 , and convert it to ammonia (NH_3), other FeMo-binding proteins with additional signaling domains are putative candidates for N_2 -sensing gasoreceptors that mediate N_2 -based gasocrine signaling. We must also consider the possibility of promiscuity of gasocrine signal-gasoreceptor and/or co-factor binding as N_2 is not the only FeMO-binding gas. Additionally, similar to how lactose levels are sensed as allolactose via the lac repressor (a sugar-sensing swodkoreceptor), N_2 may also be sensed as NH_3 via NH_3 -sensing receptors (*Drosophila* Ir92a?, but what about cytoplasmic like sGC for NO?). Identifying how cells sense N_2 *per se* or NH_3 may help us understand gasocrine signaling, causes for civilizational diseases etc.